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Rim Messaoudi, Achraf Louiza and Francois Azelart, Akkodis Research, France

Full Text: <https://aircconline.com/ijnlc/V13N4/13424ijnlc01.pdf>

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Interlingual Syntactic Parsing: An Optimized Head-Driven Parsing for English to Indian Language Machine Translation

**Pavan Kurariya, Prashant Chaudhary, Jahnavi Bodhankar, Lenali Singh and Ajai Kumar, Centre for
Development of Advanced Computing, India**

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